

THE INFLUENCE OF PRE-STRETCHING AND TEMPERATURE ON THE STATIC AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE BEHAVIOUR OF GLARE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The influence of two parameters – pre-stretching and temperature – on the static and damage tolerance behaviour of GLARE3 is examined. Results from analytical models and tests are given. The analytical models comprise a static part, which is mostly used for the evaluation of internal stresses, and a part for the evaluation of the crack propagation in the aluminium layers.

1. INTRODUCTION

GLARE (GLARE is a registered trademark of the Structural Laminates Company) is a hybrid material composed of glass-fibre reinforced UD-prepregs and thin aluminium layers. This material exhibits excellent fatigue crack properties and is therefore considered by some manufacturers as a possible structural material in future aircraft structures [1, 2].

In this paper two specific features of the material have been investigated, which may be essential if the material is used in real aircraft structures :

- o The influence of different degrees of pre-stretching. This is mostly interesting with respect to stretchforming.
- o The influence of temperature at various levels, as they are typically found in transport aircraft.

The specific material tested is GLARE3 with a lay-up of 3 aluminium layers (0.3 mm 2024 T3) and 2 layers of glass fibres, each consisting of two UD-prepregs (R-glass and AF163-2K resin) oriented at 0 and 90 degrees to the L-direction of the aluminium. The overall thickness is 1.4 mm. One major advantage of GLARE compared with monolithic aluminium is the fact that the glass fibres influence the stress distribution in the vicinity of cracks and notches. This effect is known as "crack bridging" in the literature. It is obvious that the crack bridging is highly influenced by residual stresses, which may

either be introduced by temperature changes or pre-stretching.

The theoretical model comprises a very simple analytical model for the impact of temperature and pre-stretching on the residual stresses and strains, based on the well-known laminate theory and a model for the prediction of the crack propagation. The second part of the model uses the theoretical assumptions given by [3].

2. THE INFLUENCE OF PRE-STRETCHING AND TEMPERATURE ON THE STATIC BEHAVIOUR OF GLARE

2.1 Internal and Residual Stresses at Tension Loading

Since GLARE consists of two different materials with different properties, internal and residual stresses occur during tension loading and unloading. Even in the virgin state of the unloaded material after bonding, residual stresses are apparent at temperatures different from the curing temperature, due to different thermal expansion. In the analytical model it has always been assumed that the strain is the same for all layers (2-d effects widely have been neglected). During tension loading both kinds of layers are therefore loaded according to their Young's modulus. When the aluminium starts yielding, the stress-strain curve differs from the linear elastic path, but the stress still increases, since the stress-strain relation of the glass fibres can be assumed as linear up to ultimate load. At unloading, the remaining plastic strains counteract the stresses in the fibres. Both strains and stresses have to find an equilibrium state. Due to the remaining elongation of the plastically deformed aluminium layers, the aluminium will be under compression, while the glass fibres are in tension.

Figure 1 : Comparison of Results of the Stress-Strain-Curves of GLARE3 from Tests and Analytical Model

Figure 1 shows the results of the tension tests and their analytical calculation (both at room temperature). Different specimens have been used in order to check different degrees of pre-stretching. The comparison of both curves indicates that the analytical model works very well and therefore it is clear that also the internal stresses are calculated quite well. The elasto-plastic behaviour of the aluminium has been calculated by means of the Ramberg-Osgood relation. The kinematic and isotropic hardening of 2024 T3 has also been taken into account (see e.g. [4]). Obviously, the compressive stresses within the aluminium layers are very high, if higher degrees of pre-stretching are reached. This is indicated by the fact that the material begins to yield during unloading. From this diagram it seems to be certain that no remaining strain greater than 2% may be reached for GLARE3 material ("spring back" effect).

2.2 Blunt and Sharp Notch Strength with and without Pre-Stretching

For the investigation of the blunt and sharp notch behaviour of GLARE sheets of 100 x 370 mm have been pre-stretched up to different levels (1 %, 2 %, 2.4 % and 3 % total strain). The notches have been incorporated after the stretching of the material. The notches have been chosen such that the nett cross-sectional area is 0.75 times the undisturbed cross-sectional area (i.e. the notch is a hole or a saw-cut of 25. mm).

Figure 2 : Blunt and Sharp Notch Strength of GLARE3 at Room Temperature

Figure 2 indicates the increase of the blunt and sharp notch stresses for different levels of maximum pre-stretching strains. The fact that the notch strength increases with increasing pre-stretching may widely be interpreted by means of Figure 1. In the case that all points of the plate are loaded less highly than during the pre-stretching procedure, the strain-distribution will be the same as in the case where the material has not been pre-stretched, except from an off-set of $\Delta\epsilon^{Pl}$. $\Delta\epsilon^{Pl}$ is the remaining strain at unloading after pre-stretching. When the first regions of the specimen – this is in the vicinity of the hole – are reaching the stress level of the pre-treatment these points have reached the same stress-strain relation as in the case of no pre-treatment, but the entire surrounding is capable of carrying higher loads (due to the higher stiffness). Therefore, a decrease of stress and strain occurs in the vicinity of the notch.

Surely, there are many additional effects. One major effect may be found in the sharp notch case at high pre-stretching levels. Here the off-set stress of the glass-fibres due to the pre-stretching seems to be so high that they fail earlier.

2.3 The Effect of Temperature on the Static Properties of GLARE3

Temp.	[° C]	-50	+20	+80
σ_{02}	[MPa]	275	265	252
E_{el}	[MPa]	55500	53000	47000
E_{pl}	[MPa]	15500	14000	11500

Table 1 : Static Properties of GLARE3 at Different Temperatures

Three different temperature levels (-50 , +20 and +80 ° C) have been tested. It can be derived from table 1 that the static material properties are decreasing with increasing temperature. Table 1 shows the yield-stress σ_{02} , and the tangent modulus in the fully elastic and (linear) plastic area of the stress-strain

curves of GLARE3 at different temperatures. The different properties may mostly be explained by the internal stresses at different temperatures and to some extent by the altered stiffness of the resin.

The same influence of temperature is found in the case of blunt and sharp notch stresses, both properties clearly decrease with increasing temperature. This may be interpreted in the same way as the effect of the pre-stretching. A higher temperature decreases the stiffness of the material and therefore the argumentation of 2.2 also applies here.

3. THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE BEHAVIOUR OF GLARE3

As mentioned above, the main advantage of GLARE is the excellent damage tolerance behaviour of the material. This good behaviour is due to the fact that the glass fibres are reducing the stress intensity factor (SIF) within the aluminium layers ("crack bridging effect").

3.1 The Model Used

Crack propagation of GLARE is a complex process. Different aspects have to be taken into account: the "crack bridging" effect, the delamination in the vicinity of the crack, the shear deformation of the adhesive between the layers and other factors influence the crack propagation, depending on the load history. It is not reasonable to try to take into account all effects, therefore a restriction to the most interesting influences has to be made. The basis of the used model are the assumptions made by Marissen [3] for ARALL. It is quite normal in the case of fracture mechanics to find larger differences between theory and experiments. This is the same for the present model. But the results are good enough to find an interpretation of different effects. The model itself is too extensive to be discussed in this paper, but fortunately most of the model is well documented in [3]. The main line of the used model and the few differences from Marissen's model are given as follows:

- o If a fatigue crack occurs in GLARE, this only affects the aluminium part. It is assumed – and this is confirmed by experiments under normal conditions – that the fibres are still intact. This also means that for GLARE the crack propagation depends on the size of the initial saw-cut, where also the glass fibres are cut. For the calculation of the crack propagation different models have been used, which are also known for monolithic aluminium and depend on the SIF and the R-value (Paris, Forman, Elber [5] and Newman [6]). For the calculation of the SIF different parameters have to be calculated.
- o The reduction of the SIF by "crack bridging" is based on two main effects: the reduction of the stress within the aluminium layers and the reduction of the crack opening displacement (COD). The stress which is redistributed from the aluminium layer to the fibres is called "crack bridging stress". It is assumed in the model that this stress is constant along the entire crack, where the fibres are intact. This stress depends on the size of the delamination: a larger delamination zone gives a lower crack bridging stress. On the other hand, the delamination zone grows with increasing local crack bridging stresses. Therefore, an equilibrium between both effects is found in the theory.
- o The strain of the fibres (in the vicinity of the crack) depends on the COD. According to linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) the COD is an ellipse. In the case of GLARE and ARALL without pre-straining, the delamination zone may also be approximated by an ellipse. Therefore, Marissen uses a constant fibre strain and stress. By using this approximation, the SIF may be calculated by

$$K_{AL} = c_d \sigma_{Al} \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (1)$$

where c_d depends on different correction terms, the length of the crack and initial saw-cut, the size of the delamination in the direction of the crack, the width of the specimen and the stiffness of the prepreg and laminate. σ_{Al} is the stress within the aluminium without the presence of a crack and "a" is half of the crack-length. If pre-stretching has to be taken into account, equation (1) is altered as follows :

$$K_{i,AL} = c_d (\sigma_{Al} + \sigma_{Al,0}) \sqrt{\pi a} \tag{2}$$

where $\sigma_{Al,0}$ indicates pre-stress in the aluminium-layer due to pre-stretching (keep in mind that $\sigma_{Al,0}$ normally has got a negative sign).

o Two further effects alter the SIF. One is the shear deformation of the adhesive the other is the delamination. Within the model the influence of the delamination has been used in the way of long cracks. This is only necessary, since the state of a very short crack remains relatively short in the specimens life. Both of the influences will result in an additional term K_{ad} , which increases the SIF.

o The delamination growth has been calculated by means of the energy release rate and is based on some experimentally determined parameters.

3.2 The Results

Figure 3 : Crack Propagation of GLARE3 After Different Levels of Pre-Stretching at Room-Temperature, Saw-Cut $2s = 20$ mm

Crack propagation has been tested by 160 mm wide CCT-specimens. The initial saw-cut measured $2s = 20$ mm. Maximum stress was 140 MPa at $R = 0.1$. In some cases the initial saw-cut was $2s = 6$ mm. Figure 3 shows experimental crack propagation results for different levels of pre-stretching. Two effects may easily be found from this figure: first, the crack-growth rate decreases with increasing level of pre-stretching. Second, for higher levels of pre-stretching the value of the critical crack-length decreases. Both of these effects may be interpreted from the results of the theoretical model. According to eqn. (2), the SIF decreases for compressive stresses in the aluminium layer due to pre-stretching. Secondly, the stress within the glass fibres increases as a result of the compressive stresses in the aluminium part. After all, it is obvious that the damage tolerance behaviour of GLARE is superior to the monolithic 2024 T3 behaviour.

Figure 4 : Crack-Growth-Rate for Different Initial Saw-Cut Sizes and Levels of Pre-Strain, Roomtemperature, $\sigma_{\max} = 140 \text{ MPa}$, $R = 0.1$

The theoretical crack-growth prediction model is very good in the case of material without pre-straining. But, as figure 4 indicates, the model diverges in the case of higher levels of pre-straining. There are different reasons for this behaviour. One major reason seems to be the fact that the shape of the delamination zone is not at all an ellipse any more. This fact has been proved by means of a special technique. After accomplishment of the crack-growth tests, the two outer aluminium layers have been etched in order to provide an impression of the delamination zone, which is clearly visible in the vicinity of the crack. While this zone may really be approximated by an ellipse in the case of no pre-straining, this shape is clearly altered if pre-straining occurred. The zone degenerates and shows a nearly constant extension. This fact has not only a large effect on the calculation of the delamination growth, it also falsifies the assumption of a constant fibre stress across the crack (see chapter 3.1).

One further parameter may be illustrated by figure 5. Temperature has a large effect on the crack propagation behaviour. There are different influences which affect the crack propagation.

The behaviour of GLARE3 without pre-straining is shown in figure 5a, it may be explained as follows: First, it is well known that the crack-growth rate of 2024 T3 is decreased by decreasing the temperature from room temperature (RT) to -50°C . But this is surely not the only reason. By increasing the temperature from RT to $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$, this effect must be relatively small. As indicated in chapter 3.1, the shear deformation of the adhesive plays a crucial role for the crack bridging stress and therefore for the SIF. Both, the influence of the temperature on the shear stiffness of the adhesive and the delamination behaviour are not included in the theoretical model, but it seems to be obvious that these are some driving factors of the above mentioned effects.

Figure 5 : Crack-Growth of GLARE3 at Different Temperatures and Levels of Pre-Strain

In the case of higher pre-straining, the effect of temperature is just the other way round (see figure 5b, note that the scale of the cycles is not the same as in figure 5a). This effect increases with increasing level of pre-straining. An explanation may be found as follows: for lower temperatures the coupling of fibres in the vicinity of the crack is very good. Therefore the stress in the fibres increases (see explanation of figure 5a). But, due to the high tension stress in the fibres after pre-straining, fibre failures occur at an early stage. These fibre failures influence the crack propagation in such a way that the sum of the higher crack bridging stress and early fibre failures results in a bad influence on the crack propagation.

Figure 5 also shows the fact that the damage tolerance performance of GLARE3 is superior to the 2024 behaviour, even if the temperature is varied.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Different conclusions may be drawn from the above mentioned facts :

- o The static behaviour of GLARE with respect to pre-straining and temperature is well described by a slightly modified, classical laminate theory.
- o The crack growth model reveals good results in the case of GLARE3 without pre-straining. If pre-stretching is required, the model obviously does not use adequate assumptions. Due to a lack of data, also the influence of temperature was not adequately incorporated in the model.
- o Pre-straining shows a large effect on the damage tolerance behaviour. It decreases the crack-growth rate, but also the crack length where the crack gets critical decreases.
- o While the crack-growth behaviour of GLARE3 is improved by pre-straining, the stiffness of the material is reduced, at least in compression, if higher levels of pre-straining are reached. This property is a clear disadvantage, if GLARE3 is used in common aerospace application (e.g. buckling performance).
- o Different aspects of the behaviour of GLARE3 after pre-straining have not been examined, e.g. bi-axial loading.
- o The effect of temperature may be summarized as follows: most of the static and damage tolerance properties degenerate with increasing temperature

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References

1. Ohrloff, N., Horst, P., *Feasibility Study on the Application of Glare Materials in Wide Body Aircraft Fuselages*, in: *Advanced Materials and Structures from Research to Application*, eds. Brandt, J., Hornfeld, H., Neitzel, M., Basel, 1992
2. van Oost, R.C., Slagter, W.J., van Wimersma Greidanus, B., Gunnink, J.W., *Feasibility Study of the A320 Fuselage Section 13/14 in Aerospace ARALL*, TU Delft, Report LRV-07, Delft, 1990
3. Marissen, R., *Fatigue Crack Growth in ARALL – A Hybrid Aluminium–Aramid Composite Material*, PhD Thesis, Report LR-574, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, TU Delft, 1988
4. Kossira, H., Horst, P., *Cyclic Shear Loading of Aluminium Panels with Regard to Buckling and Plasticity*, *Thin-Walled Structures*, Vol. 11, pp. 65–84, 1991
5. Elber, W., *The Significance of Crack Closure*, STP 486, American Society for Testing and Materials, pp. 230–242, 1971
6. Newman Jr., J.C., *A Crack Closure Model for Predicting Fatigue Crack Growth under Aircraft Spectrum Loading*, NASA TM-81941, 1981